

Assessing the Turkish airline industry through the lens of experience economy: A content analysis of airline experience

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p>	<p>This study aims to give readers insights into the airline experience expressly provided by the Turkish airline industry. This study employs content analysis, a qualitative research technique, to systematically evaluate textual data related to the concept of airline experience as presented on the official websites of the Turkish airline industry. The study aims to provide a detailed account of the experiences offered to customers by airline companies operating in Türkiye. The list of currently operating airline companies was obtained from the website of the General Directorate of Civil Aviation, the governing aviation authority in Türkiye. As three of the fourteen companies on this list specialize exclusively in freight, the remaining eleven companies were selected as the basis for this study. The study identifies several implications for the Turkish airline industry. Firstly, airlines should adopt a more comprehensive approach to the customer journey, integrating services across all stages of travel. Secondly, investments in digital transformation and personalization will be essential to meet future passenger expectations. Finally, airlines must recognize the strategic value of post-flight engagement and safety measures, leveraging these elements to build long-term customers.</p>
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1. Introduction

Travel has been one of the most frequent activities carried out by humanity throughout history. People travel for various reasons: education, work, psychological health, or leisure. No matter what those social, biological, and cultural forces are, the behavior of traveling has always been on the table (Pearce & Lee, 2005). Since the travel concept is widespread, it is no surprise that it attracts more attention in the research community than many other research matters. Although there are many interpretations, travel simply can be defined as a process in which people move from one place to another. During this process, people interact with other individuals, experience different locations, and finally collect perceptions about the whole experience of this travel phenomenon. In other words, travel experience can be defined as a construct that includes three phases: anticipatory phase, experiential phase, and finally the reflective phase. According to this core information, travel can be considered an activity-based process. During the process, people plan their trip, travel physically, and document their journey. However, some scholars suggest that the travel experience involves more dimensions than this. Since the travel experience is personal and every traveler perceives their

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version of the experience with different motivations and backgrounds, this construct should include interpretation and sensation. (Wang & Fesenmaier, 2013).

The travel experience is a complex construct that includes different dimensions and is experienced daily. People have been traveling for a long time with different motivations, and how they travel has changed in parallel with the technology they use. As technology provided travelers with more comfort, security, and safety, their transportation choices also varied. People had traveled barefoot or with the help of horses before technology stepped in the process. Other means of transportation, such as cars and ships, took part in travelers' lives. As the technology evolved, the options for travel also diversified drastically. It took some time for travelers to set their eyes on the sky and wonder how it would feel if they traveled like birds (Anderson Jr, 2016). It was going to reach that point, and it did eventually.

Humankind has always been an admirer of flying. This admiration led them to find different ways to fly with the help of technology. The journey that led the world to today's flight technology was not a walk in the park. Early attempts at human flight were centered on the imitation of birds. Unfortunately, so many of these flying attempts ended up with disastrous consequences. However, with ambition and relentless attempts, the Wright brothers finally made the first powered flight in 1903 (Anderson Jr, 2016). This invention was a cornerstone in aviation history. After the Wright brothers achieved this, air transportation gradually became the most vital mode of the century (Nissalke Jr, 2009).

Air transportation allows people to travel long distances securely and safely in a short period. Airline companies are top-rated comparing to the other companies which provide different modes of transportation services because they offer their customers the comfort of traveling long distances quickly. Air transportation is undoubtedly one of the most convenient and safest modes of travel, even with the advent of modern technology (Eren, 2020). Air transportation is the first option for passengers for several reasons, including its massive capacity to transport cargo, mail, and passengers. Furthermore, it offers a transportation service for long distances in a short period. The scorecard of the airline industry also demonstrates the high level of safety, which is the prominent reason for the demand it attracts (Barnett & Higgins, 1989).

It is a well-established tenet of economic theory that the supply of a given good or service will be provided immediately if there is a demand for it. Consequently, the elevated demand for air transportation has propelled the industry's growth over time. As indicated by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), civil aviation accounts for over 4.5% of global economic output. These figures illustrate the pivotal role of the civil aviation industry in the world economy and the daily lives of modern individuals (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2001).

In the context of air transportation, it is essential to prioritize the service providers. In the context of air transportation, airlines represent a primary category of service providers. An airline can be defined as a company that carries passengers and freight by aircraft for a fee with a commercial motivation (General Directorate of State Airport Authority, 2011). According to this definition, an airline's main task is to provide air transportation for freight and passengers. However, today's airline service is slightly more complex than this definition. As mentioned above, the travel experience means more than a person moving from one place to another. So is airline experience. Airline companies now provide extra services supporting their main air transportation task. Therefore, the service airlines offer to the passengers starts before they arrive at the airport at the first stop and continues until they leave the airport at their final destination. During the airline service process, the whole experience includes but is not limited to the reservation, airline services provided at the airport, ticketing and luggage handling, check-in, security and passport control, boarding to the aircraft, in-cabin services, getting off the airplane, baggage claim, again airlines services at the final destination airport and finally leaving the airport. These services provided by the airline companies in different variations give the travelers an extraordinary air travel experience. As mentioned above, the travel experience has different dimensions and is not a time-phased activity only.

Given the high level of competition within the airline industry, it is in the interest of airlines to provide the best possible service to their passengers, with the aim of offering an outstanding airline experience. It can be reasonably assumed that the aforementioned airlines will be able to maintain their competitive advantage and achieve a sustainable level of profitability. In a nutshell, both travel experience and airline experience

have their characteristics. On the other hand, there are parallel aspects to which service providers should pay attention. People who travel and utilize airlines as a part of their travel experience are picky when choosing their service providers.

To fully understand the concept of the airline industry through the lens of the experience economy, it is essential to delve into several related areas. Before conducting the analysis, the study will mention theoretical background including motivations for travel, the concept of experience economy, the concept of airline experience, components of airline experience, and finally airline safety experience. Providing some understanding on the concepts and some feature of air transportation industry along with its history will help the readers to understand the data analysis better.

Given the importance of air transportation and the concept of experience mentioned earlier, this study aims to provide readers with insights into the airline experience offered by the Turkish airline industry. The lack of a satisfactory number of studies on the matter is one of the main motivations encouraging the author to conduct this study. This research aims not only to provide insights into the airline experience of the Turkish airline industry but also to encourage researchers to take an interest in the topic.

2. Theoretical Background

The term "travel" is generally understood to refer to a person's physical movement from one location to another. It has been the primary activity of human history. It has been argued that the capacity to migrate (travel) has been a crucial factor in the survival of the human species. (Bennet, 2012). Long story short, travel is one of the main topics of human history and still is one of the most common activities carried out for many reasons.

2.1. Motivations for Travel

The topic of travel motivations is central to the research discipline of tourism management. The researchers in the era of tourism management always ask, "Why does a person travel?" (Mehmetoglu, 2004). Even though it is not easy to answer such a question (Dann, 1981), many theories have come up to respond (Huang, 2021). Some theories of motivation for travel are the push and pull model, the escaping-seeking framework, the travel career ladder model, and the travel career pattern model.

The first plausible explanation for motivations that drive people to travel is human nature. Some suggest people travel because they are intrinsically motivated to change their lives. In the literature, it is called the pull and push model. According to this model, two types of motivations drive people to travel: push and pull motivations. Push motivation factors are considered internal psychological reasons that drive people to move away from home. On the other hand, pull motivational factors are a place's features and characteristics that attract people. At the end of both motivations, people travel to another destination. Since the reasoning behind this theory is common sense, it has been widely used in multiple eras, such as marketing, management, education, and tourism (Huang, 2021).

Another theory seeking answers to motivations for travel is the escaping-seeking framework. A two-dimensional model presented by (Mannell & Iso-Ahola, 1987) seeks answers for an individual's reason for travel. According to the model, an individual is constantly affected by two motivational forces simultaneously. While one of the forces leads them to escape from their boring daily routine, the other motivates them to seek entertainment and leisure to reward themselves.

The last two travel motivation theories are the career ladder and the career pattern models. The travel Career Model has been proposed based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs motivations theories. According to the travel career ladder model, an individual with more travel experiences is likely to present more motivations related to the higher end of Maslow's model, such as love, belongingness, and self-actualization, than the other with fewer travel experiences. Unlike the travel career ladder model, the travel career pattern model does not follow the hierarchy needs of theory. However, it does relate travel motivations to travel experience as the travel ladder model does. According to the model, host-site and nature-related involvement are more critical to experienced travelers. On the other hand, other motivational factors like romance, stimulation,

personal development, relationships, nostalgia, self-actualization, and recognition seem to be more important to less experienced travelers (Huang, 2021; Maslow, 1970; Pearce & Lee, 2005).

2.2. Experience Economy

Experiences are distinct, brand-new economic offerings; they are as different from services as services are from goods. Companies in today's economy in an extensive range of industries simply wrap their services with experiences that their customers desire (Pine II & Gilmore, 1998). The purpose of experience is to create unique stimuli so that consumers will respond to these stimuli and get various feelings like pleasure and entertainment (Alagöz & Ekici, 2014). Companies trying to get customers' satisfaction and loyalty naturally respond to their customers' expectations. Finally, these consumers' expectations turned today's industries into an "experience economy." The concept was first mentioned by Toffler (1970) in their book "Future Shock" and has become very popular in today's marketing and management.

In the endeavor to foster loyal customer relationships, it is insufficient to focus exclusively on product, price and service quality. The role of experience in the entertainment industry has been a long-standing one, exemplified by the work of Walt Disney. This concept has subsequently been adopted by other businesses. To illustrate, the tourism industry has come to recognize that the provision of memorable customer experiences represents a crucial factor in achieving sustainable success. The provision of accommodation or entertainment alone is insufficient to extend the duration of visitors' stays. The airline industry is another sector that has adopted the experience economy concept. Given the transportation industry's long-standing involvement in cutting-edge technology and the fact that new technologies are driving the emergence of novel experiential genres, it is unsurprising that the experience concept is particularly well-suited to the air transportation industry. (Akel & Cakir, 2023; Pine II & Gilmore, 1998).

2.3. Airline Experience

Because of its nature, the experience concept is used in the airline industry inclusively worldwide. A former British Airways chairman declared that the people's perspective in the industry is that an airline's product transports people from one point to another on time at the lowest price possible. According to the former chairman, British Airways goes beyond the primary function of what is called the main product of an airline. The airline uses its base as a stage to create a memorable experience for its passengers (Pine II & Gilmore, 1998).

Another example of an experience concept in the aviation industry is how Chicago O'Hare Airport decorates its parking area. Different Chicago sports franchises like the Bulls, the White Sox, and so on were used on other floors to remind people which floor they parked their cars in a fun way. That way, passengers would never forget where they parked their vehicles. A simple action like this with a small cost can create a memorable, fun experience for passengers before a long trip (Pine II & Gilmore, 1998).

Another major airline focusing on "experience" is American Airlines (AA), one of North America's largest airlines. AA provides a "travel experience" tab on its official website. The menu includes different classes with different in-flight experiences, in-flight entertainment systems, and facilities to give their passengers a perfect airline experience (American Airlines, 2022). As the concept becomes a necessity in the sector. More airlines adopt their strategies to involve more experience concepts.

One of some Asian airlines that invented the concept of experience is China Southern Airlines (CSA). CSA presented its new in-flight service as a "Unique Interactive Experience." With its service, passengers can access duty-free purchase service while enjoying the entertainment system on the screen. (Southern Chinese Airlines, 2022). Another Asian airline famous for its airline experience is Singapore Airlines (SA). SA elevated the airline experience concept of its peers, airline companies. SA reflected this experience as "Elevated Travel Experience" on their websites. The airline claims to utilize five senses to give its customers a uniquely delightful experience. According to their official website, they address sight, smell, sound, taste, and touch. Their unique experience offers their passengers a traditional, extraordinary sight, batik motif in the cabin, and staff uniform details. Moreover, SA's signature scent is made of flora. In addition to the sight and smell, they also composed a unique melody inspired by the same local flora. Last but not least, the texture and the

food they serve to correspond to the touch and taste are also mentioned on their website (Singapore Airlines, 2022a).

Prior to an in-depth examination of the airline experience, it is imperative to gain a comprehensive understanding of the aviation industry as a whole. Given the distinctive features of the industry, the passenger experience is also likely to be distinctive and different from other experiences. It is therefore necessary to provide some insight into the general characteristics of the aviation industry, with a particular focus on the airline industry. It is crucial to explicitly address the factors that may influence the airline experience, including the historical development of air transportation, the significance of an airline company, the products and services offered by an airline company, the structure and dynamics of the airline industry, the business models adopted by airlines, and the role of regulatory authorities in the aviation industry.

The man has long held the ambition to become a flyer. In the present era, it could be argued that the aspiration has been realized. Nevertheless, it has not yet reached the point where one can fly with complete confidence and without encountering any issues, regardless of the natural or physical conditions present. It is anticipated that in the near future, passengers will be able to travel by air with complete confidence. It could be argued that the optimal travel experience has been achieved. In order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the airline experience, it is essential to have a clear grasp of the historical development of man's flight, from its earliest stages to the present.

To comprehend deeply, aviation history is classified under six periods: the epoch of the precursors, the pioneers of the heaviest air, the First World War, the Second World War, and the second half of the twentieth century. Humankind had to go through all these terms to reach the point that they are currently in the airline experience (Petrescu et al., 2017). The epoch of the precursors represents the time starting from the end of the eighteenth century. Until this time, people only imagined how a machine could help people to fly, and this is when the action began. This term witnessed the development of aerostation and numerous gliding attempts. Then it came "the pioneers of the heaviest air." In this period, people who were designers or adventurers attempted to fly with motor vehicles for the first time. Almost every attempt in this period was a new record, the fastest, the longest, and so on (Petrescu et al., 2017).

Military forces saw the potential of what an aircraft could achieve on a battlefield. Then, the First World War witnessed the time when airplanes started getting mass production. Aviation developed drastically, and being a pilot has become a "profession." At the end of the First World War, so many aircraft were in the militaries of many countries. Also, so many people were able to fly an aircraft. Advances in civil aviation owe so much to military aviation because of the First World War. This term is the one when commercial air transport slightly started. In the Second World War, it was no surprise that aircraft were primarily used for military purposes. The gift of this term to civil aviation was the birth of the jet engine and the radar. Again, advances in military aviation technology were transferred to the civil aviation industry when the war ended. Commercial airports started in the second half of the twentieth century, thanks to the surplus of aircraft and pilots during the wars. This term can be called the time of jets and when air transportation opened its doors to all (Petrescu et al., 2017). Looking back at the past, it is unfortunate to know the comfort and the pleasant experience of airlines today are primarily thanks to the wars that occurred back in the day. However, it would have been a big waste not to use all that surplus of aircraft and to leave all those trained pilots unemployed. Light comes after the darkest time. This phrase could be the best way to give an insight into aviation history.

In order to gain an understanding of the phenomenon of the airline experience, it is first necessary to gain insight into the nature of airlines in general. The first step towards understanding the nature of an airline is to define it according to the standards set by the relevant aviation authorities. According to Türkiye's Directorate General of Civil Aviation (DGCA), air transportation companies carry passengers and/or cargo for a fee on certain lines for commercial purposes. In addition to the definition, Passenger and freight transportation that is not within the scope of commercial air transportation and businesses that carry out air business and training activities, regardless of whether they are paid or not, are also considered air transportation companies (Directorate General of Civil Aviation, 2021). Air transportation companies are classified under four categories. These are airlines, air taxis, general aviation, and balloon companies. According to the definition made by the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure General Directorate State of Authority (GDSAA), an airline is a natural and legal person who carries passengers and

cargo with aircraft for commercial purposes in return for a fee (General Directorate of State Airport Authority, 2011). So, to consider an air transportation company as an airline, there are two conditions. First, the company must carry passengers, freight, and cargo with an aircraft. The second is that the company must provide such a service for a fee.

All activities conducted by airlines, which represent one of the two fundamental pillars of the aviation industry, are inextricably linked to those performed at airports. In other words, the majority of airline operations are conducted at airports. Airlines are required to utilize airports for the transportation of passengers, freight and mail, which constitutes the fundamental aspect of their services. Consequently, although the activities in question are the responsibility of the airlines, they are primarily conducted at the airport (Aktemur, 2021). It can be reasonably deduced from the aforementioned information that the location in question does not necessarily define the service provided.

As previously stated, the principal objective of an airline is to facilitate the transportation of passengers, freight, and cargo by air. Nevertheless, the service provided by airlines is considerably more complex than this description suggests. The outcome of an airline can be conceptualized as comprising both abstract and physical elements. To illustrate, it can be stated that the airline's product is not merely the seat purchased by passengers; it also encompasses a range of services, including those provided before and after the flight. To sum up, the outcome of an airline can be defined as a group of activities consisting of carrying passengers with an aircraft and, at the same time, meeting their needs at an acceptable cost (Atalık, 2018). These activities consist of both abstract and physical concepts. In order to comprehend the attributes of an airline's performance, it is essential to grasp the following information. The outcome is an abstract concept, primarily concerned with the provision of flight services. It is inextricably linked to the performance of the flight, as the provision of the service is contingent upon the flight taking place. The service is personal in nature, as it can only be consumed once the flight has been performed. The service is heterogeneous in that each individual perceives it in a distinct manner. Furthermore, the aforementioned characteristics preclude the possibility of storage, as the seat in question cannot be stored for use on the next flight when it is empty (Atalık, 2018).

The structure of the airline industry may also exert an influence on the quality of service provided by airline companies, which in turn affects the passenger experience. The competitive nature and tendency towards monopolistic practices provide insight into the quality of the product and the service that consumers perceive. The airline industry is one of the fastest-growing sectors globally. The airlines have high tendency to adopt the instant changes in the environment (Ertek & Taşçı, 2023). It is characterized by intense competition and rapid changes in competitive parameters. Furthermore, the merger and acquisition activities between stakeholders and the formation of airline alliances have significantly altered the sector's market structure, making it more dynamic (Yaşar & Kiracı, 2018). The structure of the industry has changed over time due to outside factors. The industry, which started with strict governmental limitations and rules, has changed drastically with deregulations in the United States of America (USA). This liberalization trend has gradually influenced the airline industries in other parts of the world. Now, even though there are some areas where airline industries have less liberal structures (because some policies aim to protect local airline companies), it is easy to say that the industry structure has been becoming more and more competitive (Yaşar & Kiracı, 2018). As a result, this competitive market allows consumers to have higher-quality services and products. Even though it is far from perfect, the airline experience that passengers have nowadays is at its best.

Another factor that might affect the airline experience of passengers is the business models of the airline companies. As a result of the airline industry being highly competitive (Doğan et al., 2020), the companies running the business in the industry look out for solutions to survive in different directions. Defining what a business model means is essential before going into details of airline business models. A business model is a company's purpose, approach to doing business, brand proposition, and strategic corporate objectives (Whyte & Lohmann, 2020). Therefore, one may claim that an airline's business model can say a lot. Airlines adopt different business models since the industry tends to be unstable and unpredictable. This tendency forces them to restructure and create flexible strategies that can respond to rapid and sudden changes in the industry. Unsurprisingly, an airline with a flexible business model can perform better in a highly competitive and turbulent environment (Nair et al., 2011).

Knowing that airlines adopt different business models so that they can be flexible enough to survive in such an unstable environment brings another question: what are the business models they adopt? There are different ways of classifying business models performed by airline companies. The business models airlines adopt are low-cost, charter, regional, hybrid, and specialist airlines. On top of that, readers should note that airlines do not strictly apply these models. On the contrary, airline companies adopt different features of each business model in accordance with (Aktemur, 2021; Whyte & Lohmann, 2020).

Another widely accepted method of classifying business models in the airline industry is to categorize airlines into two distinct groups. The first category comprises airlines that provide a basic transportation service, transporting passengers from point A to point B via aircraft. In addition to the aforementioned service, this model entails the outsourcing of all ancillary services required by passengers. The airline maintains that the provision of ancillary services is beyond the scope of its expertise and therefore not within its purview to offer directly. In contrast, the second model provides both the primary transportation and ancillary services concurrently. However, the airline offers services on the other side via other companies that are owned by the same company (Aktemur, 2021; Doganis, 2005).

Due to the inherently international nature of aviation, the industry is characterized by a multinational environment. Given its multinational character, the airline business can be regarded as one of the most international in nature. While this nature brings numerous advantages, it also gives rise to considerable challenges, particularly in the context of administration. In order to address these challenges, the international community has sought to leverage the expertise of international organizations in the management of the various aspects of the industry. These global organizations exert a profound influence on businesses operating within the aviation industry. As airlines represent a significant commercial entity within the industry, the activities of these organizations have the potential to impact the operations and services provided by airlines to their customers. It is therefore incumbent upon the reader to be aware of the role of these authorities, which provide advice to airlines on matters pertaining to their own operations.

One of the most inclusive authorities in the industry is the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), which sets the standards of operation and management activities. ICAO was established with the signing of the Chicago Convention in 1944 by 193 national governments to support coordination and diplomacy in aviation. ICAO advises governments to establish new international standards and recommended practices for civil aviation internationally. Once the advice is made, the governments of 193 countries bring worldwide alignment to their national regulations, helping to realize safe, secure, and sustainable air operations on a truly global basis. Even though all these regulations influence airline actions, it is essential to know that ICAO is not an international aviation regulator. ICAO does not have the authority to close or restrict countries' aviation industries. ICAO is only advisory (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2021).

Another influential authority is the International Air Transportation Association (IATA). It would be correct to say IATA is an association that represents 290 airlines across the world and 83% of world air traffic. It supports the industry in multiple aspects and seeks solutions for the issues that arise for airlines. IATA supports the industry so airlines can provide efficient and productive service to their passengers without compromising safety and security. IATA mentions its mission as a leading representative of the airline industry. It would be safe to say IATA is very influential on airline service, so it is a crucial factor to consider when discussing the airline experience (International Air Transportation Association, 2021). It is essential to note that both ICAO and IATA are intensively influential on the activities of airlines carry out. This indirectly affect airline experience perceived by passengers.

2.4. Components of Airline Experience

Given the distinctive nature of airline travel in comparison to other industries, it is necessary to develop a unique construct to assess the customer experience within this sector. It is evident that the existing literature on the airline experience concept is limited and that further in-depth studies are required. Even though some considerable research attempts have been made on the topic, they are mainly addressing one part of the air travel experience product and missing the rest (Bouwens et al., 2018; Etemad-Sajadi et al., 2016; Sharafkhani et al., 2021; Wattanacharoensil et al., 2017).

One research study on the topic of airline experience was conducted by Alagöz and Ekici (2014). Their research aims to study how much Turkish Airlines benefits from experiential marketing operations, brand quality, and experiential quality of services. In their study, they also seek to examine how these applications affect their customers' vacation experience and if they differ in accordance with their socioeconomic backgrounds. In their research, Alagöz and Ekici (2014) used the experience construct of Holdbrook and Hirschman (1982), assuming that the experience consists of 5 dimensions: sense, feel, thinking, act and relate. Even though they addressed the airline experience in a holistic approach, they did not mention some parts of the stages of air travel, such as post-flight or pre-flight experience, which are also very significant from passengers' perspectives. The approach to the airline experience concept must be more inclusive to cover all aspects of airline service to give the customers a memorable experience in every step of their journey along with the airline.

Aura Design (AD), in a case study titled "How to Design an Airline Experience," demonstrated the needs of business travelers and proposed an airline design in accordance with the traveler's needs. According to AD, an airline experience must be classified into consecutive stages. With respect to the order, these stages are preparation, travel to the airport, at the airport, on the plane, and finally, post-flight. It is crucial to know that an air trip does not consist of on-flight experience only. It is a pile of experiences starting before the flight and continuing afterward. As AD emphasizes these consecutive processes, classifying the experience into several stages may help airlines provide services that fit better for different passenger profiles in various stages (Aura Design, 2018).

The initial interaction of a passenger with the airline starts before the flight. This is the first chance for airlines to impress their customers. The first action for a passenger planning to travel by airline is initially to purchase an online ticket. After that, they went to their webpage for online check-in. Later, the packing process comes. Because of that, travelers also must check the items that they are allowed to carry with them during the flight. Another online information they need to access is the weight limits for their baggage. All these are essential aspects of an airline experience. At this point, a user-friendly interface is crucial in the industry. A considerable shift in preference from ticket purchases at travel agencies to using online reservation systems by passengers (Gündüz & Pathan, 2013) led airlines to invest in more convenient websites and mobile apps. Nowadays, more airlines are expected to adopt digital ticketing systems as their primary marketing strategy (Yazid & Jantan, 2017). Due to the fact that the website of an airline is very effective on the customer experience of in-flight matters, airlines must create the perfect websites to fit their customer's needs. To be able to satisfy and improve the online experience of their customers, airlines must focus on two significant factors, which are the characteristics of users and the learning factor (Ekşioğlu et al., 2013). An airline can offer its customers a personalized travel experience through these two factors. Furthermore, the airline can ensure an increase in the feeling of value and recognition of its customers (Aura Design, 2018).

The second stage of the airline travel experience is how to travel to the airport. There are limited airline options to offer when it comes to airport travel. There are so many parameters that might affect the passenger's experience on this journey, such as the city's road infrastructure, the location of the airport, and so on. Different towns have different offers for the public to reach the airport. Some airlines, like Turkish Airlines, offer their business-class flyers a complimentary exclusive drive to the airport. Luxurious vehicle rides include picking passengers up from the first destination airport to dropping them at their last destination (Turkish Airlines, 2022b). The road services airlines might offer to lay on a larger spectrum like Uber, public transportation, carshare, and more.

The next stage of the airline travel experience is the experience passengers perceive at the airport. This one can be considered one of the most significant stages after in-flight. The airport experience is a different concept than the airline experience; however, keeping these two aspects of the aviation industry apart is almost impossible. Most airline services (check-in, lounges, baggage claim, etc.) occur at the airport. In addition to the service airlines offer, the airport has its own experiences passengers go through, such as security personnel, immigration officers, and other services. Passengers may have negative experiences because of this chaotic environment. Poor connection and coordination between agents and airline ground staff mostly end up disappointing passengers since the primary goals of these staff are different and sometimes may contradict each other. Air travelers consider this combination of separate activities (airline

services, immigration, security, etc.) as a holistic judgment of the overall airport experience (Wattanacharoensil et al., 2017). To sum up, the coordination and connection with other airport staff will make the airline's business easier so they will be able to offer the best travel experience at the airport part.

The passengers use lounges at the airport before boarding. Lounges are the areas where airlines can offer various services to satisfy customers' needs. Passengers relax, have drinks, and try to enjoy their time before getting in cues. Many passengers will want to spend minimum time onboarding, check-in, and security cues. It is recommended that personalized service be provided to make the passengers feel valued and minimize the friction of the process as much as possible. Facial recognition technology not only gives minimum social interaction to speed up the boarding process but also allows airline staff to offer personalized service via the information piled up in the system from their previous flights.

Another critical stage of airline experience is in-flight experience. Many airlines provide different classes for their flight experiences. The services vary in accordance with the classes their passenger purchased. The services airlines mainly mention on their websites for their in-flight experiences are entertainment systems, different classes, airline food, and their fleet. In aviation, most airlines classify their passengers as business and economy. Depending on the airline company, this classification may get into more groups like premium, first-class, or suites (Emirates, 2022b; Singapore Airlines, 2022b; Turkish Airlines, 2022c). When a passenger is a frequent flyer traveling in business class, their needs may differ from those of someone flying economy for a vacation. The airline must be able to provide different experiences for those passengers in the same cabin. While a business class flyer may want to focus on his presentation before the conference, an economy class flyer may wish to enjoy his time during the flight as much as possible with drinks and entertainment systems.

Finally, the post-flight experience offers passengers transportation and accommodation. So many airlines also provide city tours for their passengers if they have a stopover in their base cities. In this way, they can give a city experience while using the city's fame to get their company at the top of the choice list for passengers (Turkish Airlines, 2022a).

2.5. Airline Safety Experience

Safety is a crucial element of the aviation experience, and It has always been a top priority in air travel. Now, the airline business has flourished into a massive industry. The concerns of passengers regarding safety must be addressed by the airlines, especially after the COVID-19 virus has hit the sector deeply (Bakirci, 2020). After the flights started with the virus mutating, airlines wanted to comfort their passengers and ensure they felt safe. To achieve that, many airlines take part in their websites to inform and update their customers on the virus and the health rules. While some airlines, like Emirates, provide health insurance against the COVID-19 virus for their flights (Emirates, 2022a), most offer their passengers hygiene kits to keep them and their staff safe on flights (Akpur, 2021). It does not hurt to say that Covid 19 added a new element to the airline experience concept, and the airline industry could not resist this change. Almost no airline company does not have a COVID agenda in post-pandemic times.

3. Methodology

This study employs content analysis, a qualitative research technique, to systematically evaluate textual data related to the concept of airline experience as presented on the official websites of the Turkish airline industry. Content analysis is the most effective research method for interpreting and analyzing textual, visual, or audio content. It enables researchers to draw inferences by identifying and analyzing the specific characteristics of messages within the content being studied. The foundation of content analysis is its systematic approach, which involves a sequence of steps that guide the researcher through the analysis process. Qualitative content analysis is characterized by its systematic nature, where all relevant material is considered, and coding is checked for consistency to enhance the trustworthiness of the study (Elo, Kääriäinen, Kanste, Pölkki, Utriainen, & Kyngäs, 2014). This systematic approach is crucial for ensuring that the findings are credible and replicable, which is a hallmark of rigorous research. In conclusion, content analysis represents a robust and flexible research methodology that allows for systematic examination and

interpretation of various forms of content. Its structured approach, coupled with its adaptability to different research objectives, makes it an invaluable tool for researchers across disciplines. By employing rigorous coding and analysis techniques, researchers can derive meaningful insights from their data, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of the phenomena under investigation. Based on the information given related to content analysis, it is considered as the best fit as a research technique for the research. The study aims to provide a detailed account of the experiences offered to customers by airline companies operating in Türkiye. The list of currently operating airline companies was obtained from the website of the General Directorate of Civil Aviation, the governing aviation authority in Türkiye. As three of the fourteen companies on this list specialize exclusively in freight, the remaining eleven companies were selected as the basis for this study. In the end, Turkish Airlines, SunExpress, Pegasus Airlines, Freebird Airlines, Corendon Airlines, Tailwind Airlines, MGA Airlines, SouthWind Airlines, Airanka, Ajet, and BBN Airlines were objected as the sample of the study.

To examine the experiences offered by these companies, their official websites were analyzed, and relevant information was systematically presented. During data collection, only textual content was considered. By focusing solely on textual data explicitly mentioning "experience," the analysis targeted content directly relevant to the study's objectives. This approach minimizes the risk of irrelevant or tangential data inclusion. Only English-language versions of the websites were analyzed to maintain linguistic consistency and to reflect the accessibility of information for international passengers.

The data collection process was carried out between 20th September and 26th October 2024. Given that the airline experience consisted of consecutive stages, every tab/page was checked to withdraw textual data mentioning the concept of "experience". A coding framework was developed based on themes grounded in existing literature, including the following categories: preparation stage, travel to the airport, at the airport, in-flight experience, and finally, post-flight experience. The themes would break into sub-components along the data analysis as airline travel is a detailed multi-processed phenomenon.

To enhance inter-rater reliability, the coding process was reviewed by two independent researchers who cross-checked the categorizations. Discrepancies in the coding process were resolved through discussion until consensus was reached, ensuring consistent interpretation of the textual data.

4. Findings and Discussion

This research is focused on the airline industry in Türkiye. The official website of the Turkish Directorate General of Civil Aviation was consulted to obtain a comprehensive list of airline companies operating within the Turkish aviation sector. Table 1 lists current airline companies operating in the Turkish airline industry. As indicated in the table, the list comprises of 14 companies, including those that provide cargo and mail transportation exclusively. Consequently, MNG Airlines, ULS Global, and ACT Airlines, which do not offer passenger transportation services, have been excluded from the analysis in this study.

Table 1: Airline Companies Operating in Türkiye

Name of the Airline Company	Operation Focused
Turkish Airlines	Passengers and Freight
Pegasus Airlines	Passengers and Freight
MNG Airlines	Freight Only
Freebird Airlines	Passengers and Freight
ULS Airlines	Freight Only
Corendon Airlines	Passengers and Freight
My Cargo Airlines	Freight Only
Tailwind Airlines	Passengers and Freight
MGA Airlines	Passengers and Freight
Southwind Airlines	Passengers and Freight
Airanka	Passengers and Freight
BBN Airlines	Passengers and Freight
Ajet Airlines	Passengers and Freight

Source: SHGM, 2024

Prior to undertaking a detailed examination of the textual content, it is essential to identify the key areas of focus for the airlines on their respective websites. While the emphasis placed on specific services differed between companies, the textual data exhibited a noticeable overall pattern. The primary focus of the airlines was on the concept of experience, with an emphasis on comfort and hospitality. The airlines attempt to capture the attention of their passengers by highlighting the luxury services especially available in business class or the tailored services they offer. Another frequently mentioned service is the lounge and airport services. The majority of airlines offer additional services to their passengers. Additionally, airlines offer passengers the opportunity to experience culinary offerings. The quality of the food is of primary importance in determining the overall mood of passengers, and airlines are acutely aware of the impact they can have on their passengers' experiences. Another concept that airlines frequently emphasize on their websites is the provision of tailored and personalized services. Regardless of the stage at which the passenger is in their air transportation journey, the airlines describe the services they offer as tailored and personalized for their passengers. The final term that is commonly used to describe the experience is entertainment systems. The service, which is mainly part of the in-flight experience, is also an essential tool for providing an unforgettable experience for passengers.

Describing the airline experience as a consecutive process led the author to the idea of classifying it into several stages before the analysis textual data. Processing the analysis accordance with that approach will provide a clearer insight for the reader. The findings are categorized into five primary stages of the airline travel experience: preparation, travel to the airport, airport experience, in-flight experience, and post-flight experience. Additionally, safety was considered as cross-cutting theme, given its heightened significance in the post-pandemic era. Even though safety has been one of the most significant components of air travel, COVID 19 pandemic highlighted the matter as it became more appearing than ever in the eyes of the passengers.

Figure 1: Stages of Airline Experience
Source: Tailored by the Author

The preparation stage is becoming increasingly dominated by digital tools designed to enhance convenience and efficiency. Turkish Airlines is a notable example in this regard, offering passengers a comprehensive travel guide, entitled "*Fly Good, Feel Good,*" which provides practical advice for a seamless journey. Similarly, Pegasus Airlines emphasizes the provision of facilities designed to reduce stress, such as the "*Primeclass Lounge*" and digital check-in options. SunExpress places significant emphasis on the convenience of booking and customization afforded by its loyalty program and "*retroclaim*" features, thereby demonstrating a clear commitment to customer-centered service. While the majority of airlines emphasize user-friendly interfaces, there is considerable variability in the depth of information and personalization provided. For instance, charter carriers like Freebird Airlines offer minimal pre-flight engagement compared to full-service airlines like Turkish Airlines. This can be considered as a remarkable example of airline business models affecting airline experience concept.

Another stage mentioned often on the webpages is travel to the airport. It is notable that services at this stage of development are less prevalent across the industry. Turkish Airlines' chauffeur-driven "*Exclusive*

Drive" service for Business Class passengers represents a particularly noteworthy and exemplary offering. Similarly, SunExpress provides tailored transportation solutions in collaboration with *"Welcome Pickups,"* emphasizing a personalized and seamless journey to the airport. Nevertheless, the majority of airlines require passengers to arrange their own transportation, with minimal integration of ancillary services or collaboration with third-party providers. This gap in the market represents an opportunity for growth, as improved airport accessibility is a key factor in passenger satisfaction. So far only a few companies offer this service and make it an experience for their passengers.

It is widely acknowledged that the airport experience represents a pivotal point in the customer journey, with notable discrepancies in the quality of service provided by different airlines. Turkish Airlines offers a premium experience through its comprehensive lounge facilities, which encompass gourmet cuisine, relaxation areas, and dedicated workspaces. Similarly, Pegasus Airlines employs lounges as a means of improving passenger satisfaction, whereas SunExpress places an emphasis on the optimization of airport procedures through the implementation of expedited security protocols. Budget carriers frequently lack dedicated lounge services, which places them at a competitive disadvantage. The coordination between airline and airport staff is identified as a recurring challenge, with some websites emphasizing the importance of reducing friction during the check-in and boarding processes.

The in-flight experience displays the greatest divergence among airlines. Turkish Airlines has established a standard of excellence with its *"Flying Chefs"* program, which provides passengers with high-quality, customizable dining experiences in both Business and Economy classes. Furthermore, additional features, such as the latest entertainment systems and premium amenity kits, are provided in order to cater to the diverse needs of passengers. SunExpress offers a variety of seating options, allowing for flexibility in accommodating different passenger profiles. Freebird Airlines places an emphasis on inclusivity, addressing the specific needs of pregnant passengers and travelers with reduced mobility. Budget airlines such as Tailwind and MGA Airlines prioritize cost-efficiency over luxury or personalization, offering basic services at the lowest possible price.

Turkish Airlines has once again demonstrated its commitment to innovation in this category, offering pioneering program such as *"Stopover in Istanbul"* and *"Touristanbul."* These initiatives have the potential to transform layovers into culturally enriching experiences, enhancing the customer experience beyond the scope of the flight itself. Such initiatives illustrate the potential for enhancing brand loyalty by extending the customer experience beyond the mere act of travelling by air. Other airlines, such as Pegasus and SunExpress, place a primary emphasis on the provision of efficient baggage handling and transportation services. The absence of comprehensive post-flight program among the majority of airlines suggests that there is an untapped opportunity to engage with passengers after their journey.

The findings demonstrate a notable discrepancy in the manner in which Turkish Airlines conceptualizes and operationalizes the airline experience across the five stages of travel. Turkish Airlines demonstrates consistent excellence, exemplifying a model of comprehensive service integration that aligns with global best practices. In contrast, other carriers frequently prioritize cost-efficiency, which often results in the provision of a more limited range of services. It is evident that there is a discrepancy in the airline industry with regards to the conceptualization and implementation of the passenger experience. This can be attributed to the varying business models adopted by different airlines, which often result in disparate perceptions of the passenger experience. In light of these observations, it can be confidently asserted that the business models of airlines have a significant impact on the experiences they offer to their passengers.

The findings highlight the importance of designing a seamless, end-to-end customer journey. Turkish Airlines provides an exemplar of the efficacy of integrating pre-flight, in-flight, and post-flight services into a unified narrative. Program such as *"Stopover in Istanbul"* and *"Touristanbul"* have the dual benefit of enhancing passenger satisfaction and serving as strategic marketing tools for both the airline and the destination.

The issue of digital transformation and personalization represents another area that requires the attention of researchers. It is evident that there is a shift towards digital platforms across all stages of the travel experience. Airlines that invest in the creation of user-friendly websites, mobile apps, and the implementation of personalized services are better positioned to meet the evolving expectations of their

customers. To illustrate, the loyalty program and digital magazine of SunExpress and Pegasus Airlines, respectively, demonstrate how airlines can leverage technology to engage passengers. Nevertheless, the industry as a whole has yet to fully capitalize on data analytics and AI-driven personalization in order to deliver experiences that are genuinely tailored to the individual.

Furthermore, the airport experience was identified as a potential competitive advantage. It has been demonstrated that airport lounges and fast-track services represent pivotal points of contact that have the potential to exert a considerable influence on passenger perceptions. Full-service airlines are aware of this and are investing in premium lounges and streamlined check-in processes as a result. Nevertheless, budget carriers frequently neglect the airport experience, thereby failing to distinguish themselves in a competitive market.

The most pertinent stage of competition in the context of the overall airline experience is the in-flight experience. The provision of in-flight services continues to represent a significant area of differentiation. Turkish Airlines' emphasis on high-quality dining and entertainment is well-suited to the needs of premium passengers, while SunExpress' flexible seating options are designed to cater to the diverse travel profiles of its passengers. It is imperative that airlines continue to innovate in this area, striking a balance between cost-efficiency and passenger satisfaction.

The post-flight stage represents an area of opportunity that has been relatively underexplored by many airlines. Turkish Airlines' initiatives demonstrate the potential for extending the customer relationship beyond the flight, thereby fostering loyalty and brand advocacy. Airlines that fail to address this stage run the risk of losing valuable opportunities for engagement.

The intensified emphasis on safety is indicative of a shift in passenger priorities. It can be reasonably deduced that airlines which integrate these measures into their broader experience strategy are more likely to gain the trust and loyalty of their passengers. It is also important to emphasize that the safety measures of airlines are also affected by the recommendations and rules imposed by international and local authorities. These measures are certainly more appearing on webpages as the passengers are paying more attention to the matter along with the pandemics. With or without pandemics, the safety is always going to be on the table for airline companies.

5. Conclusion

The study identifies several implications for the Turkish airline industry under the concept of experience economy. Firstly, airlines adopt a more comprehensive approach to the customer journey, integrating services across all stages of travel. Secondly, airlines consider investments in digital transformation and personalization essential to meet their passenger expectations. Finally, airlines recognize the strategic value of post-flight engagement and safety measures, leveraging these elements to build long-term customer relationships.

Although each airline has their own focus in different matters and stages of air travel, there are several common grounds that most airlines invested in. The differences between these airline experiences might be caused by the fact that they adopt different business models. It was also concluded that the authorities are also affecting the travel experience up to some point.

This article gives an overview of the topic of travel experience, specifically the concept of airline experience. Even though the era of airline management and airline marketing attracts a massive amount of interest from researchers, the general picture shows us that the topic of airline experience specifically requires more contributions from the research community. More vital collaboration between industry professionals and academia may also contribute to the topic and accelerate the comfort and safety of the experience customers perceive on their air travel journey. This article aims to contribute to the topic of airline experience as a primary study. Literature review proves that more similar studies are required in the topic. Also, studies examining the passengers' and professionals' perspective on airline experience may also help to gain deeper insights for a better experience.

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